

Management of Sick Sinus Syndrome with Syncope: A Case Report

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Abstract

This report describes the clinical management of a 79-year-old male patient admitted with syncope, ultimately diagnosed with Sick Sinus Syndrome (SSS), a complex disorder of sinoatrial node dysfunction. The case was encountered during clinical rotations at Pineta Grande Hospital's Emergency and Cardiology Departments. The patient's atypical presentation, coupled with significant comorbidities including malignancy, necessitated urgent intervention that diverged for standard protocols. Initial assessment revealed episodes of marked bradycardia and sinoatrial block confirmed by telemetry and electrocardiography, alongside exclusion of reversible causes. Imaging ruled out acute cerebrovascular events. Given the risk of potentially fatal pauses, a definitive pacemaker implantation was performed promptly, stabilizing the patient's cardiac function and enabling further oncologic management. This case underscores the critical importance of recognizing syncope as a primary manifestation of SSS, particularly in vulnerable populations where timely cardiac stabilization may be lifesaving. It further highlights diagnostic challenges and the need for individualized treatment strategies aligned with contemporary guidelines. The clinical course illustrates the relevance of multidisciplinary care and individualized management.

Key words: Electrophysiology; Pacemaker; Sick Sinus Syndrome; Sinus Node Dysfunction; Syncope.

Introduction

Sick Sinus Syndrome (SSS), or Sinus Node Dysfunction refers to a spectrum of disorders characterized by abnormal impulse formation or propagation from the sinoatrial node (SAN), impairing its pacemaking function.

Clinically, SSS manifests as sinus bradycardia, sinus pauses or arrest, sinoatrial exit block, or alternating brady- and tachyarrhythmias (brady-tachy syndrome), often associated with chronotropic incompetence during exercise or stress^[1–7,33,34].

SSS primarily affects older adults due to age-related SAN degeneration, but it can occur at any age. The prevalence is approximately 1 in 600 adults over 65 years, with a median age of 74 in one cohort of patients over 21 years^[2,8,19]. Men and women are equally affected^[20].

The etiology of SSS can be divided into *intrinsic* and *extrinsic* factors. *Intrinsic* causes include:

- Degenerative fibrosis of SAN (historically thought to be age-related, idiopathic);
- Ion channel dysfunction^[2,28];

- Remodeling of the SAN^[9,16], occurring in heart failure and atrial fibrillation;
- Infiltrative disease processes, including connective tissue diseases, haemochromatosis, sarcoidosis and amyloidosis^[26,32];
- Atherosclerotic changes of the sinus node artery in 65% of patients, may contribute to chronic ischemia and subsequent fibrosis of the SAN but are not considered as major cause of SSS^{[4][10]}.

Extrinsic factors include:

- Pharmacologic agents (e.g. beta-blockers, calcium channel blockers, digoxin, sympatholytic medications, antiarrhythmic medications and lithium)^[11,12];
- Metabolic disturbances (e.g. hyperkalemia, hypokalemia and hypocalcemia)^[12];
- Autonomic dysfunction can mimic or exacerbate SSS via neurally mediated bradycardia in vasovagal syncope, neurocardiogenic syncope and carotid sinus hypersensitivity^[13-15,36];
- Hypothyroidism, hypoxia, hypothermia and toxins^[16,17].

While infrequent, sick sinus syndrome has been documented in association with other cardiac pathologies, including Brugada syndrome, a genetic channelopathy that carries a risk of sudden cardiac death^[16,17].

Sign and Symptoms

SSS is typically progressive. Early stages may be asymptomatic; however, as the disease advances, symptoms reflect end-organ hypoperfusion. Cerebral hypoperfusion represents the most frequently observed complication, with ~50% of patients experiencing presyncopal episodes or frank syncope^[17-19,36]. Other signs of inadequate perfusion may include transient dizziness, cognitive impairment, fatigue, palpitations, anginal symptoms, congestive heart failure, ischemic cerebrovascular events, nonspecific gastrointestinal disturbances, and oliguria^[20-24,32].

Classification

Traditionally, SSS was subdivided into electrophysiological subtypes:

- sinus bradycardia,
- sinus arrest,
- sinoatrial exit block, and
- bradycardia–tachycardia syndrome

to reflect the heterogeneous nature of sinus node dysfunction^[1,2,4,30,32]. This classification provided a mechanistic framework for understanding the syndrome's manifestations.

However, contemporary clinical practice, as reflected in the 2021 ESC/EHRA and 2018 AHA/ACC/HRS guidelines, emphasizes a symptom-driven diagnostic approach. SSS is now primarily defined by the presence of sinus node dysfunction associated with clinically

significant symptoms, such as syncope, presyncope, fatigue, or documented sinus pauses exceeding 3 seconds, particularly when occurring during wakefulness^[22–25,31].

This evolution reflects a shift from a purely electrophysiological to a more patient-centered and outcome-oriented classification^[30,31].

Diagnostic Criteria

The diagnosis of SSS is established through a combination of clinical presentation and electrocardiographic evidence, as recommended by recent international guidelines^[22-25,36](*Tab. 1*).

Category	Criteria/Description	Clinical note
Clinical symptomatology	Syncope, presyncope, dizziness, fatigue, exercise intolerance	Main clinical manifestations; helps identify symptomatic SSS
Documented sinus node dysfunction (ECG)	Resting sinus bradycardia (<50 bpm), sinus pauses/arrest (>2 s wake, >3 s sleep), sinoatrial exit block, chronotropic incompetence on exercise	Confirms electrical abnormality; core diagnostic evidence
Exclusion of reversible causes	Medications, electrolyte imbalances, systemic illnesses	Rule out extrinsic factors contributing to bradycardia
Symptom-rhythm correlation	Temporal association between symptoms and rhythm abnormalities; via 12-lead ECG, Holter, or implantable loop recorder	Strengthens diagnosis by linking symptoms to documented arrhythmia
Additional diagnostic tools	Carotid sinus massage, tilt-table testing, cardiac imaging	Supports diagnosis; excludes alternative causes of syncope or bradycardia
Associated arrhythmias	Atrial fibrillation or other arrhythmias frequently coexist with SSS	Influences clinical presentation and management strategies

Table 1. Summary of Diagnostic Criteria for Sick Sinus Syndrome (SSS), adapted and created by the author, based on major international guidelines and peer-reviewed literature^[1,4,7,12,22,25-28,30,31,33-36].

Here is presented the case of a patient admitted with syncope who was ultimately diagnosed with SSS requiring urgent pacemaker implantation.

Case Report

Anamnesis

A 79-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department at 08:56 a.m. on July 16, 2025, after a reported syncopal episode. The event was not preceded by prodromal symptoms and occurred during a pre-operative surgical workup. The patient exhibited retrograde amnesia. His past medical history included hepatic and pancreatic head carcinoma, for which he was awaiting surgical admission, as well as a previous bladder polypectomy, dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension, benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), and a prior laparoscopic removal of a pancreatic cyst. He reported no known allergies and was on a regular regimen of the following medications:

- Atorvastatin 10 mg
- Escitalopram
- Tamsulosin
- Olmesartan/Hydrochlorothiazide 40/12.5 mg
- Nebivolol 100 mg
- Alprazolam.

Physical Examination

The chest exam revealed diffusely harsh breath sounds. His abdomen was soft and non-tender,

with no reported hematochezia, hematemesis, or melena. Urinary output and bowel movements were regular. Peripheral pulses were present, strong, and synchronous.

The patient was awake and alert, with retrograde amnesia. Neurological examination showed isochoric, reactive pupils and no focal deficits. Vital signs were stable (BP 150/70 mmHg, HR 63 bpm, sO₂ 98%), and laboratory tests were unremarkable except for mild hyperglycemia; cardiac biomarkers were negative.

The initial ECG showed sinus rhythm at 65 bpm with first-degree AV block (*Fig. 1*).

An urgent head CT excluded acute cerebral ischemia.

At cardiology consultation, the patient denied chest pain, dyspnea, or palpitations, and showed no signs of congestion. Telemetry monitoring revealed episodes of marked bradycardia (HR 25–30 bpm), consistent with sinoatrial block.

Transthoracic echocardiography demonstrated normal biventricular size and function (LVEF 55%), mild mitral and tricuspid regurgitation, normal estimated pulmonary artery pressure, and no pericardial effusion. The conclusion of the cardiology consultation was syncope in a patient with electrocardiographic evidence of sinoatrial blocks. Admission to the Cardiology Department (CD) was indicated, but a bed was not available at that time.

Imaging

To rule out a cerebral ischemic event, an urgent head CT was performed. The scan revealed no acute densitometric changes in the cerebral nervous tissue. There was a mild enlargement of the supratentorial ventricular system and slight asymmetry of the lateral ventricles, with the right side being more prominent. The fourth ventricle was in a normal position, and the pericerebral and pericerebellar subarachnoid spaces were within normal limits. Midline structures were centered, and calcified atheromatosis changes were noted in the carotid siphons.

A cardiology consultation was requested.

Cardiologic Consultation

At the time of the consultation, the patient was calm and denied chest pain, dyspnea, or palpitations. There were no signs of peripheral or pulmonary congestion. Heart sounds were rhythmic with no pathological murmurs, and hemodynamics were stable.

Telemetry monitoring revealed episodes of marked bradycardia (HR 25–30 bpm), consistent with a sinoatrial block. A carotid sinus massage was performed (*Fig. 2*).

An echocardiogram showed a left ventricle with normal end-cavity dimensions and wall thickness, with normal global systolic function (EF 55%). The left atrium was not dilated. The transmitral flow pattern was normal. The mitral valve had a normal morphology with

mild regurgitation. The tricuspid aortic valve showed a normal systolic opening and mild regurgitation. The aortic root and ascending aorta had a normal caliber in the visualized section. The right chambers were of normal size with normal longitudinal function of the

Admission and Procedure Report

The patient was monitored until a CCU bed became available and was admitted at 11:45 a.m. on July 17, 2025, in stable condition for the implantation of a dual-chamber pacemaker due to sinoatrial block.

Figure 1. ECG diagnostic findings of SSS: It reveals a first-degree AV block. Image captured by the author at Pineta Grande Hospital (Castel Volturno, Italy).

right ventricle. There was mild tricuspid regurgitation, from which a normal pulmonary artery systolic pressure (PAPs) was estimated. There was no pericardial effusion, and the inferior vena cava had a normal caliber and respiratory excursion.

The conclusion of the cardiology consultation was syncope in a patient with electrocardiographic evidence of sinoatrial blocks. Admission to the CD was indicated, but a bed was not at that moment available.

The implantation was performed under local anesthesia with continuous monitoring of vital signs (HR, RR, sO₂, and non-invasive BP).

Local anesthesia was administered with 20 cc of lidocaine hydrochloride at the left subclavian site. Venous access was obtained via left subclavian vein catheterization using the Seldinger technique, preceded by angiography of the left subclavian–superior vena cava axis to confirm patency.

Right ventricular angiography was performed to visualize the true ventricular apex in the right oblique projection and the septal region

in the left oblique projection, identifying the apical, mid, and basal segments to localize the mid-septal target implantation site.

subcutaneous tissue and skin were closed with interrupted sutures.

Figure 2. Positive response to the carotid sinus massage (CSM). It shows a profound asystolic pause (7.5 sec) triggered by the maneuver confirming a severe cardioinhibitory form of carotid sinus hypersensitivity. Image captured by the author at PGH.

A skin and subcutaneous incision was made in the left subclavian area. A subfascial and subpectoral pocket was created.

Electrocautery was used for hemostasis. Two active-fixation leads were introduced percutaneously and positioned respectively in the mid-septal region of the right ventricle (Abbott 58 cm, MRI compatible) and right atrium (Abbott 52 cm, MRI compatible). Acute pacing, sensing, and impedance parameters were optimal.

Leads were secured with non-absorbable sutures and connected to an implantable pulse generator (Abbott Zenex DR MRI compatible) placed in the subcutaneous pocket. The

Antibiotic therapy was administered post-procedure.

A follow-up chest X-ray on July 19, 2025, at 10:12 confirmed the presence of the dual-chamber pacemaker in the left pectoral pocket (*Fig.3B*). The pulmonary fields remained normally expanded with diffuse bronchovascular markings. The diaphragm and costophrenic angles were unremarkable, and cardiac silhouette was within normal limits.

The patient was discharged at 10:00 a.m. on July 20, 2025.

Discussion

Syncope in an elderly patient requires evaluation for reflex-mediated causes (such as

vasovagal syncope or carotid sinus hypersensitivity), orthostatic hypotension,

emphasize symptom–rhythm correlation, documented sinus node dysfunction, and

Figure 3. *A Baseline chest X-ray (AP view) performed upon admission to the ER. The image shows a normal cardiothoracic ratio with no signs of acute pleuropulmonary lesions. It excludes structural abnormalities or acute complications before proceeding with the diagnostic CSM and subsequent surgical intervention. B Post-procedural chest X-ray (PA view): generator in the left pre-pectoral pocket with leads successfully positioned. Image captured by the author at PGH, July 2025.*

cerebrovascular events, and arrhythmias^[13–15,18–20,22]. In this case, sudden loss of consciousness without prodrome, retrograde amnesia, and the context of a resting state, strongly favored a cardiac etiology^[17,21,23].

Early telemetry and ECG monitoring documented episodes of profound bradycardia with sinoatrial block, supporting a diagnosis of SSS^[1–7,9,25–29,36]. Reversible causes, including electrolyte disturbances, hypothyroidism, and drug-induced bradyarrhythmia, were systematically excluded during the initial assessment^[11,12,25,27]. Clinically significant sinus pauses, defined as exceeding 3 seconds during wakefulness or 2 seconds during sleep, were observed in this patient^[25–29,36], fulfilling the key diagnostic criteria for SSS outlined in the 2021 ESC^[22–25] and 2018 AHA/ACC/HRS^[24,25] guidelines, which

exclusion of extrinsic factors. Optional diagnostic tests, such as pharmacologic challenge (e.g., atropine) or electrophysiological study, are typically reserved for ambiguous or borderline presentations^[26,36]. In this case, however, the telemetry findings provided sufficient evidence, making their omission an appropriate example of clinical prioritization^[26,36].

Why SSS Is Often Underdiagnosed

SSS remains underrecognized in clinical practice due to several contributing factors. Its presentation is often non-specific and insidious, especially in older adults, where symptoms such as fatigue, dizziness, or cognitive slowing may be attributed to aging or comorbidities^[17,20,21]. Moreover, arrhythmic

episodes may be transient and therefore not captured during standard ECG evaluation^[25,26,36]. In the absence of continuous or prolonged rhythm monitoring, the

Timeliness of Intervention

The decision to proceed with urgent permanent pacemaker implantation was driven by two critical factors:

Figure 4. Cardiac Stabilization Flowchart of Sick Sinus Syndrome in Oncologic Patients. Adapted by the author.

correlation between symptoms and electrical abnormalities may go unnoticed^[25,26].

In this patient, the initial ECG was non-diagnostic, and only continuous cardiac telemetry revealed sinoatrial block episodes. This underscores the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion, particularly in patients presenting with unexplained syncope, and the need to extend rhythm monitoring when initial findings are inconclusive^[25,26,36].

- the presence of symptomatic bradyarrhythmia with high-risk pauses, and;
- the patient's oncologic status, which necessitated rapid cardiovascular stabilization to safely initiate or resume cancer therapy^[25–29,36].

According to the 2021 ESC guidelines, permanent pacing is indicated in patients with symptomatic SSS and documented sinus arrest or sinoatrial block^[25–27]. Similarly, the 2018 AHA/ACC/HRS guidelines recommend device implantation in symptomatic

individuals when a clear correlation exists between symptoms and sinus node dysfunction^[28,29].

In a different clinical context, such as a non-oncologic patient with fewer comorbidities and stable hemodynamics, a more extensive diagnostic workup, including optional pharmacologic testing or electrophysiological study, might have been reasonable before definitive therapy^[1,2,12,25,27,36]. In this case, however, the balance of urgency and risk clearly favored prompt intervention. Early pacing likely prevented recurrent syncope or cardiac arrest, underscoring the importance of timely recognition and management of high-risk bradyarrhythmias^[1,2,12,25–29,36] (*Fig. 4*).

Conclusion

This case underscores the diagnostic complexity of SSS, particularly when syncope is the sole clinical manifestation of underlying sinus node dysfunction^[1–4,36]. In elderly patients, intermittent bradyarrhythmias may go undetected without vigilant, prolonged rhythm monitoring, especially in the absence of prodromal symptoms or initial ECG abnormalities^[17–19,25,28,35]. This phenomenon has been aptly described as a “*silent sinus, silent heart*”.

In patients with active malignancy, prioritizing hemodynamic stability before initiating or continuing oncologic therapy adds an additional layer of urgency to clinical decision-making^[12,25,27]. In this context, prompt

recognition of symptomatic bradyarrhythmia and timely implantation of a permanent pacemaker, guided by current international guideline recommendations, was both appropriate and potentially life-saving^[25–29,36].

This case highlights the critical importance of applying recommendations from the ESC, 2021 and the AHA/ACC/HRS 2018 in a patient-centered, context-sensitive manner^[25–29,36]. Careful clinical reasoning, supported by a high index of suspicion and timely diagnostic data, remains essential for preventing recurrent, potentially fatal events.

Ultimately, this report demonstrates both the diverse clinical manifestations of SSS and the vital role of clinician judgment in translating evidence-based guidance into decisive, individualized interventions^[1–4,25–29,36].

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